

CONSUMER PSYCHOLOGY ON PHYGITAL STORES

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ABSTRACT

The researcher claims in the current study that marketing technologies would see a change from the offline to the website. At the beginning of 2020, the Covid-19 pandemic broke out in China, which quickly transformed into a global public health crisis with the fastest outbreak, the widest spectrum of contamination, and the hardest to monitor in the world's entire history. During the epidemic, people across the globe were suspended from all social events and kept at home. Given the fact that the expectation of the pandemic appears to be high, the buyer economy experienced a major blow in the 2020 primary quarter. Several retail organizations are putting their trust in the launch of phygital stores to deal with the crisis with the Covid-19 episode step by step regulated around the globe. The researcher aims to orchestrate the change that retailers are experiencing in the Covid-19 crisis. From the point of view of shoppers and marketers, the researcher does this intending to provide rules and describe how retailers can deal with this phenomenal circumstance. The purpose of the study is to examine the function of phygital stores by using customer attitudes. A comprehensive literature review is highlighted which provided a close understanding of phygital stores and buyer behavior during the Covid-19 emergency.

Keywords: Buyer Behaviour; Covid 19 Pandemic; Phygital Stores; Retail Marketing.

INTRODUCTION

The events of the year 2020 have utterly remodelled the manner of life, particularly once it involves searching. Whether or not it's replenishing a product or stocking abreast of home items, shoppers do it all online- browsing, looking, and shopping for. There saw raised online store creations between Aprils to May could be compared to the previous year. With new online storefronts to capture the eye of a growing digital shopper population, expectations for quick, resistant e-commerce experiences are on the rise. If the amount spent on multiple purchases increases during an online auction, researchers found that shoppers were more likely to buy an additional item they did not intend to purchase when they first visited the site (Hall et al., 2020). While this is also obviously based on certain behavior experiments, as it was carried out on travellers to a flourishing e-commerce website, spending their own money, this has extra external importance. In any case, as transactions were provided, these results provide evidence that panic buying would eventually increase online purchases without cannibalizing other goods (Akram et al., 2018; Lo et al., 2016). As a result, buying is a crucial topic that should be more investigated within the online community. Another relevant reason why website designers should try to maximize user purchases as is already suggested on the website. They are less immune to more spending if visitors to the website spend additional money. We assumed that people with higher wages were more likely to panic because their disposable income was higher (Qaisar et al., 2018). We live in a digital world, where online marketing has

become an important platform. Surely to enhance your business there are many things to be considered and new business models got to be created. The researcher tries to focus on the objectives to explore the change in buying behavior in the pandemic situation, to identify the drivers of implementing phygital stores, and evaluating the trends in the retail market economy (Chastel et al., 2019). It is very important to pursue a rigorous scientific method in the course of performing a research investigation in order to present and analyse the findings of the study and to include them in the study. The descriptive research design is used to support the seamless operation of the project in order to accomplish the goals of the study.

Statement of the problem

The introduction and acceptance of technologies by shoppers and retailers blurs the gap between online and offline shopping networks. Generations are moving into an age of convergence of all platforms to create a smooth shopping experience. In the present case, to survive this COVID-19 crisis, retailers need to transfer their offline marketing to online (O2O marketing). Now the customer can use their laptop or cell phone to purchase a garment from a supermarket or put an order on an online marketplace, they can opt to have their merchandise shipped to home or pick it up from a local store. They can also connect on social media with sellers and communicate with their customer service workers on their websites via messenger (Chang et al., 2014). The hygiene and hazard factors in the COVID pandemic time have added to the expanded selection of online business channels among customers who have either been not dynamic in advanced purchasing or favored customary channel for contact and purchase factor before making buys (Hobbs, 2020). These clients have additionally been, as an outcome, pushed towards web-based business relieving the danger of COVID compression while adding to the development of the area (Addo et al., 2020; Butu et al., 2020). As a result, consumers are heading towards an online-channel approach and retailers need to shift their shopping strategy (Fei Gao, 2016; Gao & Su, 2017). To generate more revenue and sales, retailers need to follow the strategy of online channels. However, the big challenges facing retailers are inventory visibility, customer expectation, and centralized data management in implementing this strategy. Indian retailers are now increasingly implementing a multi-channel marketing plans to improve their exposure and keep consumers interested (Gandhi, Vajpayee, and Gautam). However, mercantilism product through multiple channels isn't identical to Omni-channel selling, which could be an additional advanced idea that aims at providing seamless expertise of searching to customers across channels and building a complete. This research will help offline retailers who try to switch their physical store to a digital one (physical + digital = phygital store) as it will expose the emerging enthusiasm of retailers in their buying actions towards the Omni-channel strategy and customer attitude. In the ecommerce industry, companies have to take advantage of every opportunity that can be found. Impulse buying is one such solution. Triggering this type of customer behavior is a great way to achieve quick sales! Basically, impulse buying means getting something spontaneously, without planning this purchase or researching the market to compare different options and find a better deal.

For ecommerce businesses, impulse buying is one of the main engines for sales.

The lockdown has disrupted the last leg of the supply chain, which facilitates over 85% of the country's shopping. Moreover, the reports of economic times revealed the declining trend in impulse buy during the covid time. While most consumer products are now available online, impulse purchasing has taken a hit. To deal with it, manufacturers are exploring new marketing avenues to reach consumers. This analysis will discuss the role of digital technology in the climate of online channels, which in turn will offer an overview of emerging developments that will be useful for online retailing. Retailers will be able to appreciate the transition from offline retailing to online retailing with the aid of this study. As a result, retail firms should rely not only on fixing the rapid bounce back in usage at the conclusion of the pandemic, but even after the shortcoming of the bounce back, get ready prototypes for standardizing use.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Why do people purchase something on impulse?

So, what drives impulse buys?

In addition, what can marketers do in the store to encourage them?

It is essential to study the reasons behind impulse purchase.

There are several reasons why people tend to do this. Most notably, people make impulse purchases based on their emotions and feelings, past experiences, or if they think that they get a good offer.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Buying Behavior during COVID-19 pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic is causing an upset in the retail marketing business, to which organizations need to adjust. The stay-at-home rule restricted the normal business activities and the marketers were forced to start their offline retail business to online business, the e-commerce business is seeing an increased buying behavior of people in green and orange zones for non-essential goods (Pantano et al., 2020). The overwhelming response of the shoppers indicates that e-commerce plays a significant role even in a crisis. This reminds us of the importance of implementing a new habit of buying pattern for the consumers. A few retailers have responded to the crisis quickly, showing plenty of various intercession types. The fast-changing technology world has transformed the consumer path and thus created new retail market models (Godara & Bishnoi, 2019). With the advent of innovations, the behavior of consumers towards shopping and the approach of the retailer to create a smooth shopping experience for them have changed dramatically. Covid-19 is transforming the way Indians buy goods as the virus has impacted a change in buyer behavior for internet company receipt and advanced purchase capture (Koslow & Lee, 2020). Out of the main creating economies in the world including China, Brazil, Indonesia, Thailand, and the Philippines, the flood in the inclination for the online divert is keener in India, as indicated by an examination by Facebook India and Boston Consulting Group. The present emergency has quickened patterns that were

at that point in progress, for example, the ascent of Amazon and natural nourishments and the decay of retail establishments. Before the pandemic, the greatest boundary to expanded infiltration in online shopping for food was purchaser timidity about checking out it: buyers who looked for staple goods online used to be almost certain to do so once more (Addo et al., 2020). Since the pandemic has constrained an enormous part of the populace to dive in requesting food supplies online just because it has empowered the section to skip a very long time ahead in the pending channel blend move. The new state of utilization offers open doors for brands in classifications, for example, at leisure to discover and serve pockets of interest among customers who are investing fundamentally more energy at home ("India's e-Commerce Growth Propelled Due to COVID Might Come at the Cost of More Online Frauds" - The Financial Express, n.d.). Underlying this pattern, in any case, is the way that buyers have essentially curtailed the number of outings they make, prone to maintain a strategic distance from visit communications with others due to COVID-19, however, have expanded the absolute exchange size for each excursion (Butu et al., 2020). For food merchants, this adjustment in shopper conduct has significant ramifications for grouping choices, and it raises new difficulties for the advertisers of drive add-on things. Without a doubt, the condition of the corona virus itself will firmly impact buyers' definitive choices about buying. In reality, in any case, every industry is feeling various impacts. Computerized exchange entrance was the absolute most significant indicator of more grounded execution during the emergency and was about twice as significant as the COVID-19 introduction variable. Organizations that quickened their advanced and off-premises plan before the emergency are being remunerated. It is progressively significant for eateries to quicken their computerized request age and urge clients to create clingy propensities during the emergency that will profit them in the ensuing recuperation. Over numerous classes, for example, family unit care, individual consideration, new food, and bundled food, online business reception looks higher than the other five nations (Alauddin et al., 2015). In this digital era, customers are more demanding as they are more knowledgeable and technology-empowered. Therefore a marketer, as well as retailers, has to change their traditional strategy of doing business. A significant explanation for the transformation in the retail sector is the shift in consumer conduct (SULTANA & UMA, 2014). Retail businesses need to realize that the rebound in consumption after the end of the pandemic is not due to a sudden increase in social spending power, but because consumers urgently need to restore the normal level of buying behavior through the stimulation brought by consumption. Retail businesses should not only pay attention to deal with the rapid rebound in consumption after the end of the pandemic but also prepare plans for the normalization of consumption after the rebound weakness (Lo et al., 2016). Hygiene and risk factors also led to increased e-commerce platform acceptance by consumers who have either been inactive in digital shopping or have chosen a conventional touch-and-feel channel before making transactions.

Need for Phygital Stores

The Covid-19 pandemic has driven the planet into unforeseen well-being and financial emergency, shifting consumer lifestyles, economic crisis and propensity, and even the way partnerships function. Customers will turn towards shopping in a way that is advantageous,

protected, and tidy now like never before and the internet business room meets these needs. As the e-business space keeps on developing internationally, it is likewise hardening its toehold in the Indian commercial centre (Tronvoll, 2008). Today lockdown limitations have driven innovation disinclined customers towards utilizing innovation for the conveyance of food and online shopping of basic items. All things considered, this will bring about more purchasers progressing to the internet looking for basic and unimportant items over the long haul because of accommodation, convenience, advantages of cleanliness, and change of propensities (Moravcikova & Kliestikova, 2017). This is a manner that could additionally move the development in the web-based business space. With the e-business blast, we are watching changes in rehearses and an essential requirement for complementarity between physical stores and the virtual universe of web-based business and computerized innovation. This is what is alluded to as 'phygital', a portmanteau of 'physical' and 'digital'. Digital offers significant favorable circumstances for customary stores, by boosting footfall and upgrading the in-store client involvement in new advanced innovations (Sinha & Kim, 2012). Physical and digital are in this way corresponding and not contradicted. New determined physical stores naturally perceive clients when they enter, either utilizing man-made consciousness or facial acknowledgment (which presents issues with the GDPR in any case) or by advanced ID employing the IoT (associated objects fitted with a chip that recognizes clients). Over recent months, there have been two big increases in their consumers shifting to their e-commerce. These coincide with the circuit breaker in February and in April. The brands that have been able to reduce the impact of stores closing have had another channel for their consumers to shop in (Xu & Huang, 2014). By convincing consumers to pick up online orders at their local supermarkets, physical stores are looking for an advantage over e-commerce platforms and other e-tailers (Verhagen & Van Dolen, 2011). In reaction to last year's fiasco, the renewed focus on store pick-up comes after millions of holiday packages were left stuck after a late influx in express-delivery orders overwhelmed retailers.

DISCUSSIONS

Retailers are as of now ready to anticipate what kinds of retail strategy genuinely sway the buying behavior. Over time, promotions are going to keep on getting progressively custom fitted to the person (Mittelstaedt, 1998). Migration of customers from the offline to online medium has been influenced the marketers to implement the phygital stores which are a lifesaver in the emergency. Marketers are going to keep on turning out to be smarter and progressively installed in our everyday lives because of the fast change in the buyer economy and behaviour (Erasmus & Overwater, 2010). In the future, phygital stores have the potential to make the marketing life easier, for both the consumers and marketers that inspire and stimulate the decision making faster than others (M-Commerce: Experiencing the Phygital Retail - Google Libros, n.d.). Visibility and synchronization have a positive effect on online retail networks, where commodity, consumer and inventory data are the biggest challenges to Omni-channel retail (Fei Gao, 2016). The researcher has not discussed drives and challenges associated with phygital-channel retail organizational management.

Suggestions

Here are some recommendations on how to implement impulse buying to boost store revenues.

Keeping in view of present manoeuvrings of the business community, the basic purpose of the study is to make marketers know how to improve the terms and conditions offered and presented in the saleable product feature.

- Choose the products wisely

The best impulse products are simple products. These products do not require much explanation as it is understandable. It makes it even more perfect when things are small and inexpensive.

- Trigger the right psychological points

Generating unexpected purchases by focusing on positive aspects of the mind. For example, to create a sense of urgency with a given start-up offer or to make it seem like customers are getting a good deal by creating value in the form of discounts.

- Carefully consider where to place impulse products (Layout)

This part is all about making these products visible so that your customers can stumble upon and buy them. Where can the product are placed?

Around the most popular items

Related products

Mention them closer to the shopping cart and checkout

Keep in mind that it is important to make them noticeable and eye-catching.

- Focus on products with a low initial price

Setting the price of products with lower original prices is about 2 or 3 times more than you really should.

However, when using these online store tips, it should be remembered that the most important thing is to carefully consider the intended audience, to understand which type of products will be suitable for random purchases by those audiences.

With all of this in mind, the catalog should only include offers of the best products that are suitable for people of all ages, interests, and income levels.

CONCLUSION

Around the same time, a huge number of online customers change their actions to prefer extra productivity and convenience places major pressure on today's web-based industry and online retailers. The ultimate fate of the web-based organization will be characterized by how they plan to react. Some choose to evacuate the grating that interferes with the overall rhythm of transforming the most faithful to uncommon clients. Besides this, they continue to ensure that

online identities are stable and accounts are safe from the power of takeover. As state-by-state stay-at-home demands are lifted, offline market deals need to level out and therefore move to a higher growth pace for online businesses than they are currently (Chin et al., 2005). The outcomes uncovered that it may prompt a bounce back in utilization after the finish of the pandemic, however, this bounce back is thought and brief. This study recommends that retail organizations need to understand that the bounce back in utilization after the finish of the pandemic isn't because of an unexpected increment in social spending power, but since buyers critically need to re-establish their buying behavior from offline store to an online store, most importantly the "Phygital stores" (Chastel et al., 2019). As of now, though the behavior changes are moving to fully modify the retailing scene and trade in general for such a long time to come. In this time of COVID-19, the study found that it is important in the transition to online shopping due to comfort, ease of use, and hygiene benefits.

Future scope

Retailers are as of now ready to anticipate what kinds of retail strategy genuinely sway the buying behavior. Over time, promotions are going to keep on getting progressively custom fitted to the person (Lo et al., 2016). Migration of customers from the offline to online medium influenced the marketers to implement the phygital stores which are a lifesaver in the emergency. Marketers are going to keep on turning out to be smarter and progressively installed in our everyday lives because of the fast change in the buyer economy and behavior. In the future, phygital stores have the potential to make the marketing life easier, for both the consumers and marketers that inspire and stimulate decision making faster than others. Visibility and synchronization have a huge effect on online channel retail, where an object, consumer, and stock details are the key barriers to omnichannel retail (Bhattacharjee, 2011). As it can be, these developments should be used to retain a strategic gap from the coordination of agreements with workers that is difficult to contend with some of the time. There were scarcely any consumers who considered these developments friendly and entertaining. The Researcher did not take into account the expense effects of these developments that could diminish the eagerness of distributors to launch the phygital shops. The scientist has not investigated drives and hindrances identified with the association of the executives of phygital-channel retail.

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Conflict of Interest

No Conflict of Interest

REFERENCES

1. Addo, P. C., Jiaming, F., Kulbo, N. B., & Liangqiang, L. (2020). COVID-19: fear appeal favoring purchase behavior towards personal protective equipment. *Service Industries Journal*, 40(7–8), 471–490. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2020.1751823>
2. Akram, U., Khan, M. K., Hui, P., Tanveer, Y., & Akram, Z. (2018). Development of E-commerce: Factors influencing online impulse shopping in China. *Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations*, 16(2), 29–47. <https://doi.org/10.4018/JECO.2018040102>

3. Alauddin, M., Hossain, M. M., Ibrahim, M., & Hoque, M. A. (2015). Perceptions of consumer impulse buying behavior in the super store: A case study of some selected super store in Bangladesh. *Asian Social Science*, 11(9), 68–76. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v11n9p68>
4. Bhattacharjee, A. (2011). Quarterly CONTINUANCE :MIS Quarterly,25(3), 351–370.
5. Butu, A., Brumă, I. S., Tanasă, L., Rodino, S., Vasiliu, C. D., Doboş, S., & Butu, M. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 crisis upon the consumer buying behavior of fresh vegetables directly from local producers. Case study: The quarantined area of Suceava County, Romania. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(15), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17155485>
6. Chang, H. J., Yan, R. N., & Eckman, M. (2014). Moderating effects of situational characteristics on impulse buying. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-04-2013-0074>
7. Chastel, A., Grondin, S., Baland, J., & Maniere, I. C. (2019). Phygital Boom May Lead To Luxury Implosion. *Global Fashion Management Conference, 2019*, 514–514. <https://doi.org/10.15444/gfmc2019.05.06.02>
8. Chin, C. Y., Water, S., & Swatman, P. M. C. (2005). *AJIS Vol 13, No. 1 September 2005 THE VIRTUAL SHOPPING EXPERIENCE: USING VIRTUAL PRESENCE TO MOTIVATE ONLINE SHOPPING*. 13(1), 239–253.
9. Erasmus, N., & Overwater, I. E. (2010). Research proposal Research proposal. 1–4.
10. Fei Gao, X. S. (2016). Omnichannel Retail Operations with. *Management Science*, June, 0–15.
11. Gao, F., & Su, X. (2017). Omnichannel retail operations with buy-online-and-pick-up-in-store. In *Management Science* (Vol. 63, Issue 8, pp. 2478–2492). <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2016.2473>
12. Godara, S., & Bishnoi, V. K. (2019). A study on influence of website quality on online impulse buying behavior of Indian consumers. 21(10), 1497–1511.
13. Hall, M. C., Prayag, G., Fieger, P., & Dyason, D. (2020). Beyond panic buying : consumption displacement and COVID-19 buying. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-05-2020-0151>
14. Hobbs, J. E. (2020). Food supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 68(2), 171–176. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cjag.12237>
15. Koslow, L., & Lee, J. (2020). COVID-19 Consumer Sentiment Snapshot # 2 (p. 9).
16. Lo, L. Y. S., Lin, S. W., & Hsu, L. Y. (2016). Motivation for online impulse buying: A two-factor theory perspective. *International Journal of Information Management*, 36(5), 759–772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2016.04.012>
17. M-Commerce: Experiencing the Phygital Retail - Google Libros. (n.d.).
18. Mittelstaedt, R. (1998). THE millionaire next door: The surprising secrets of america’s wealthy. In *Journal of Macromarketing* (Vol. 18, Issue 2). Government Institutes. <https://doi.org/10.1177/027614679801800210>
19. Moravcikova, D., & Kliestikova, J. (2017). Brand Building with Using Phygital Marketing Communication. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 5(3), 148–153. <https://doi.org/10.18178/joebm.2017.5.3.503>
20. Pantano, E., Pizzi, G., Scarpi, D., & Dennis, C. (2020). Competing during a pandemic ?Retailers ’ ups and downs during the COVID- 19 outbreak. *Journal of Business Research*, 116(May), 209–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.05.036>
21. Qaisar, A., Sial, M. A., & Rathour, K. (2018). Understanding impulse buying behaviour of customers through the lens of different marketing related promotional practices. *Journal of the Punjab University Historical Society*, 31(1), 23–35.

22. Sinha, J., & Kim, J. (2012). Factors affecting Indian consumers' online buying behaviour. *Innovative Marketing*.
23. SULTANA, S., & UMA, K. (2014). A study of consumers' general characteristics influence on impulse buying behaviour. *International Journal of Commerce and Business Management*, 7(2), 354–362. <https://doi.org/10.15740/has/ijcbm/7.2/354-362>
24. Tronvoll, B. (2008). Customer Complaint Behaviour in Service Customer Complaint Behaviour in Service. *In Business*.
25. Verhagen, T., & Van Dolen, W. (2011). The influence of online store beliefs on consumer online impulse buying: A model and empirical application. *Information and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2011.08.001>
26. Xu, Y., & Huang, J. S. (2014). Effects of price discounts and bonus packs on online impulse buying. *Social Behavior and Personality*. <https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2014.42.8.1293>